

5.2.4 Response of Different Genotypes/ Varieties of Ridge Gourd for Resistance to Mosaic Disease Under Field Conditions of Rajasthan

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Ridge gourd [*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb.) L.] is one of the important warm season vegetable crop which belong to cucurbitaceae family and grown in different parts of India. Mosaic disease is an economically important disease of cucurbits and distributed throughout the tropical and subtropical regions of India. It has emerged as potential threat in the production of ridge gourd under field conditions of Rajasthan. Host resistance is one of the most important components for management of mosaic disease owing to problems associated with chemical and biological control. A field trial was conducted during summer season of 2012 to screen 22 ridge gourd genotypes/varieties (AHRG-23, AHRG-28, AHRG-29, AHRG-30, AHRG-31, AHRG-33, AHRG-35, AHRG-43, AHRG-44, AHRG-46, AHRG-48, AHRG-49, AHRG-50, AHRG-52, AHRG-53, AHRG-56, AHRG-57, AHRG-59, Arka Sujath, Pusa Nasdar, Swarna Manjri and Swarna Uphar) against mosaic disease at Research Farm of ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner with normal cultivation practices. No plant protection measures were applied against this disease. Data on disease incidence was recorded during growth period of the crop and genotypes/varieties were categorized for resistance. Among 23 ridge gourd genotypes/varieties, none was found immune against mosaic diseases. Only two (one genotype 'AHRG-29' and one variety 'Pusa Nasdar' showed resistant with 10.0% disease incidence, 14 genotypes/varieties were categorized as moderately resistant up to 25% disease incidence and 06 genotypes such as AHRG-23, AHRG-33, AHRG-46, AHRG-48, AHRG-52,